

Transcripts

These are the transcripts of the interviews conducted for “Achieving Cost-Effective Testing For Serverless-Based Applications.”

The participants all chose to remain anonymous. All participants besides #4 consented to being recorded.

The people conducting the interviews are Edvin Danielsson and Gregory Sastrawidjaya. Their first names have been used to indicate who is talking, and the participant is simply indicated with “Participant:” when they are speaking.

These interviews were initially transcribed via Outlook’s transcribing tool, and then manually validated by the two interviewers.

Participant 1

INTRODUCTIONS

Edvin: All right. But I guess we'll just get straight to the actual interview. So we have our first segment, which is the introduction questions and you can keep your answers pretty short to these ones. You don't have to go all out. It's just to get some initial introductions basically. So the first question is, how big is the enterprise that you work for?

Participant: Uhm, do you mean the actual company or the industry we work within?

Edvin: The actual company.

Participant: Okay, so I would describe it as a medium sized company. We have around 400 to 500 employees that I would say around half of those are or probably a lot, probably more than half are engineers.

Edvin: Okay, uhm, what is your development experience in years?

Participant: I'm coming up to four years now.

Edvin: Okay, very nice. What is your testing experience in years?

Participant: I would say around a year or two of proper testing.

Gregory: Can I budge in?

Edvin: Sure.

Gregory: What programming background do you have?

Participant: Programming background, uhm, what specifically?

Gregory: Like, tell us about yourself. Like what– what– You know. Like when did you start programming? What were you into?

Participant: Okay, so my very humble beginnings were around the age of 12 or 13. I started working with Java and I worked with Java. Ever since then, so for the past 10 or 11 years, I was mainly focused on a video game called Minecraft. I mostly developed modifications for the client of the game and the different servers of the game, and from there I transitioned more into graphics programming. I dealt with libraries such as OpenGL and DirectX. But after that, I'm mostly focused on web development, developing systems for enterprises such as the one I work for currently. In my day to day, I mostly work with Java and Python, and nowadays I do a lot of work with the actual DevOps, setting up infrastructure, setting up testing environments and similar.

Edvin: Nice.

Gregory: Nice nice.

Edvin: I can keep going I guess then.

Gregory: Yup, keep going!

Edvin: So what is your software development methodology, A.K.A. in what way does your enterprise work?

Participant: Well, the company itself likes to do Scrum and Agile. That's the official methodology of the company, but my team specifically sort of deviates from that since our line of work is a bit more specific, I would say. We sort of do scrumban, like a combination of Scrum and Kanban. But yeah, we– I would say it's very high paced so we don't really do sprints. We have a priority that we need to do and instead of doing Sprint planning, we sort of have regular refinement sessions where the goal for the following period is sort of defined and refined, and yeah I'd say that's about it.

Edvin: Alright alright, uhm, what serverless providers do you currently use in your enterprise?

Participant: We currently use mostly AWS. And I think some parts of the company use Azure, but I personally only work with AWS.

Edvin: Alright, what product does your enterprise offer that uses these serverless infrastructures? Like what are you making?

Participant: Uhm... I would say we have a range of products. It's not a specific product, but overall it's all services for cars. We have a range of services, for instance, software for call centers, then just simply software for cars to connect to and stuff like that.

TESTING SERVERLESS

Edvin: Alright alright. Okay, well, those were the introductory questions. Now we're just gonna ask you some— a bit more verbose questions, I guess. Regarding, like, how you test serverless; so what are the most important problems you find when you test serverless applications?

Participant: I would say uhm... that's kind of a tricky one, because I would say we sort of face the same problems with serverless and outside of it, and that is the confidence to regularly deploy our software. I think the whole purpose of testing is to have that confidence to click that deploy button and know that everything will work out in the end. But for serverless specifically, I would say: is faithfully recreating the environment that the software runs in.

When we work outside of serverless, you can sort of easily recreate the environment like set up the frameworks you need, the infrastructure you need, and sort of just put in the data that you need to test. But with serverless it's a bit more specific. A lot of the times it's based on events. When something happens somewhere, this piece of code will run and the output will be sent somewhere else and, uh, when we talk about serverless providers specifically, a lot of other pieces of infrastructure are involved to sort of make the whole flow work. So it's not only your code that needs to be tested, it also needs to be tested when it's integrated with other services. Uh, yeah, I would say that.

Gregory: Let me ask a question, would you say, I know you don't have, I know you haven't worked— have you worked with the server?

Participant: Personally, no.

Gregory: OK, would you say that it's difficult to faithfully recreate this environment when you test serverless systems?

Participant: I wouldn't say that is difficult. It's more time consuming and it can get quite costly.

Gregory: Costly in what sense?

Participant: Well, I would say the only true faithful recreation of a serverless environment is actually testing. Your serverless application is on the cloud, and to actually test it you need to run it in the cloud, and that obviously costs money. There are ways to sort of recreate those environments locally, but they are not the true experience you're getting from deploying it to your serverless environment and testing it with true services. Most of the time there are just mocks of the actual service that sort of use your file

system to emulate what happens in the cloud. And that can help you in the sense that you are 90% sure that everything is fine, but then again, you don't know if it'll actually work until you deploy it.

Gregory: All right. Yeah, I'm done.

Edvin: I guess I'll move on with the questions we have; what types of testing do you typically perform on serverless applications?

Participant: I would say it's the same sort of test that you would perform for any sort of application. You have your unit tests, you have your integration tests, end-to-end tests and they all serve their purpose. But I would think that the most important part of the serverless testing are those integration and end-to-end tests. Unit tests can only get you so far.

Edvin: Okay, yeah, that checks out with what we've read as well. Uhm... how do you test the integration between serverless functions and other services or components in the entire architecture?

Participant: Well, there's two ways you can go about that. You can deploy the service and test it in the cloud, and you can try to test it locally with some sort of emulator. In case of AWS, we use a framework called Localstack...

Edvin: Mhm.

Participant: ...which emulates uh, all of the— all different AWS services on your machine and you are able— you are able to connect all of those services with your serverless function and sort of get the idea of what's going to happen when you deploy. But it's not like I said earlier, it's not the true experience. So, even though we do this local testing, we still deploy to the cloud and use custom software to perform all sorts of different tests to cover different scenarios, different acceptance criterias. And I would say that is our end goal to have fully functional tests in the cloud, not just locally.

Edvin: Okay, moving on with the— are there any traditional testing approaches that you feel are ineffective or inapplicable when you test serverless systems?

Participant: What are you considering traditional testing approaches?

Edvin: That's a good question. *Laughs* Greg do you know—

Gregory: Like testing locally for instance. Like when you say that simply testing as a unit is not as prioritized as testing in like, like testing the end to end integration of these different systems and services

Participant: Uhm.

Gregory: Like like if you were to design the system, how would you like, would you say that there are certain ways of approaching testing the system in a serverless context versus having without like— how do I explain this? Let me— let me rephrase myself, I'm sorry. If I if I had a system and if let's say I didn't have

any serverless infrastructure whatsoever. Would there be a certain way you would approach testing that system versus testing a system that uses serverless infrastructure that would that you would find sort of like OK, like that's somewhat ineffective to do such a thing or that's something that I wouldn't really consider in a— in an infrastructure that doesn't use serverless systems? If you know what I'm— do you understand?

Participant: Uhm, yeah, I think so.

Gregory: Okay.

Participant: I mean the big point with serverless applications is that most of the time they are event driven. For instance, something happens in a database, I want to take that information and pass it into my serverless app and do something with it and pass it on along the chain somewhere. And one of the bigger problems with just unit tests, you can't really test those events. You can sort of generate your own events based on what you think happens, but the only true way to test those events is if you actually have a database, put something in it, and that event is generated by the cloud and then it's passed into your function. So, unit tests I would say work to only test the business logic of your code, but they don't cover what happens when your function gets an actual input when it's deployed. So I would say a lot more prioritization is done on end to end integration testing rather than unit testing. Like unit tests will just tell you, yeah, the code works as you expected to locally. Like if you were to run this function independently of this application: “Oh yeah, it works”. But it doesn't tell you how it'll work when you deploy it.

Edvin: Yeah.

Gregory: Nice, nice.

Edvin: Nice, all right, we're gonna ask some questions regarding how you measure tests and cost effectiveness. So uhm, with cost effectiveness, we wanna ask how do you define the concept of cost effectiveness when it comes to serverless testing?

Participant: I honestly wouldn't know how to answer that.

Edvin: Yeah, but like, what do you think, like initially when we say the word cost effectiveness? If you like, what does that mean when you hear it?

Participant: In my mind, cost is more often than not directly related to the performance of the actual system. Like if one part of your system takes ages to do something, that means that resource is in use longer than it should be, which naturally just drives up the cost of your whole operation. So I would say that, regardless of the application being serverless or not, the cost mostly depends on how you utilize your resources.

Edvin: Yeah, it's like time and money spent, basically.

Participant: Yeah.

Edvin: Then we're all on the same page, that's good. Greg, you wanna take the questions?

MEASURING & COST EFFECTIVENESS

Gregory: Yeah, yeah, exactly. So yeah, because serverless computing is based on a pay per use model. What we're trying to figure out is how to achieve these testing results while we minimize testing costs. Especially when as you said, the only true way to test serverless applications is through deploying it into the cloud and running it in production. So because it's pay per use, we found out that it could be expensive to test such functions. Yeah. And so with that being said, can you provide an example of a situation where you identified the cost inefficiency in testing? And if so, how did you address it?

Participant: You can give me a minute to think.

Gregory: Yeah, no worries.

Edvin: No problem.

Ten seconds pass.

Participant: Okay, I would say this with a lot of the serverless functions that we do... hm... most of the sort of invocation time of the function is not really spent, uh, on the actual logic that the function performs. But I would say the biggest costs we saw were during the actual startup of the function. So for instance on AWS specifically, I don't know about other platforms. Depending on the language you use to write the function, the startup time of the function can go down or up significantly. So for instance, if you're writing Java serverless functions, the startup time is quite high compared to if you're— compared to writing it in Python, for instance on AWS. As of now, Python has the... it has like the minimal startup time and a lot of our functions before were written in Java. And just because of that startup time alone, most of them were written in Python. And that just by doing that we can see a big cut in costs.

Gregory: Would you— would you say that... so would you say that simply just changing, or not changing the programming language— but more like being familiar with the serverless provider you have and— and the different sorts of and the way and knowing how that serverless provider works is important to achieving cost efficiency?

Participant: I would say so. Because from what I've noticed a lot of serverless functions are not huge. They are very compact pieces of code that serve a specific purpose, so if designed correctly they will not hold up your system like they will execute in a time I would say from 100 to 500 milliseconds, which is not done a lot when you put it into a bigger system. I would say a lot of the cost usually just comes down to people not to being familiar with what they're using and misconfiguring things in the end.

Gregory: When you say misconfiguring, What would you mean with that? Would you mean the amount of resources you put into each and every serverless function?

Participant: That is one thing. Hmm... like the amount of memory and the compute power the function uses. Another thing is for instance batching your input into the function. With on AWS, a lot of the input that comes into the function can be batched. So a single invocation can process multiple entries. And if you just process entries one by one, that means more invocations. For every entry you get, you will get one invocation, and you usually pay per invocation. So if you can process multiple things in a single invocation. That will sort of bring down the cost naturally.

Gregory: All right. How would you say, would you say your app is designed for like small bursts of these implications or do you say they're— would you say that— like, I'm trying to ask, but the way your app is designed, do you mostly get cold starts or like, every now and then like, like is there a lot of idle time?

Participant: Uhm... hm, like the way I can put this, the activity of our system really depends on the amount of cars that are on the road right now I would say. So it can be inactive from time to time, but I would say it's a pretty steady stream of information coming in.

Gregory: Okay. All right, if I think I'm done with that line of questioning. But if that's the case, what strategies would use to manage and reduce these costs when testing serverless applications?

Participant: Hm hm hm, I guess having a way to monitor the resource usage of your application. In our case specifically, we use multiple monitoring tools such as Datadog to see how specific parts of the system will function, and in some cases we also monitor how specific lines of code function in production. So I would say just keeping an eye on cost and actively trying to see how to reduce it. Like what are the bottlenecks of your system, and maybe those bottlenecks are what's causing the increased costs.

Gregory: All right. Uhm, when you— because you mentioned you work in DevOps, if I understand you correctly and maybe all the whole system. Or am I misunderstanding?

Participant: I do a lot of everything, some development, some DevOps.

Gregory: OK, would you say there are any best practices for testing serverless applications using CI/CD?

Participant: If there are best practices, I'm not really aware of them. This mostly comes from experience and from problems we faced before, like a lot of our solutions come from the actual problems we experienced with testing these applications.

Gregory: Do you have a certain issue off the top of your head that you might remember that, uh... yeah, do you have any certain scenario off the top of your head... that could be, eh... anti cost efficient— I guess cost inefficient that was cost inefficient but you know?

Participant: In my experience, not really.

Gregory: Okay, let me keep asking some more... okay, if you could redesign your current product, what changes would you make to make some testing server less easier?

Participant: That's a big one.

Edvin: Yeah, hypothetically, then.

Participant: I'm not sure I would change anything.

Gregory: Okay. Would you say that the way your organization runs things is pretty much on point to how you would expect for cost efficiency?

Participant: I would say so. Like being cost efficient is a pretty big thing for my organization, especially in times like this where it's not the easiest financial situation for anyone. It's always a big effort within the organization to cut down costs and be more efficient with the resources we use.

Gregory: Okay, then, because you mentioned that your company wants to be as cost efficient as possible, what key performance metrics and yeah— metrics in general that you would monitor in a serverless architecture to make the serverless architecture or serverless infrastructure, shall I say, more cost efficient?

Participant: I feel like that's a bit out of my area of expertise. I don't think I can give you a good answer to that one.

Gregory: Okay, like, totally understandable. Like for instance, maybe, maybe for instance like technical depth. Like if there's something that, for instance, you know, writing code and trying to test it out in the serverless infrastructure or in a serverless context. And then it turns out that this way is a waste of time and that way is a waste of time. So perhaps technical depth, perhaps, you know, collaboration with colleagues is a bit difficult with regards to certain ways you test things. Like is there anything that you can come up with that might be a sort of difficulty or pitfall that we can then perhaps like as we research this that we can then translate to metric?

Participant: Uhm, I mean all you said earlier these serverless infrastructures they are pay, pay per use, so I would say writing efficient code that doesn't necessarily have to be clean code, but efficient code that is good enough to not waste resources. Like, as long as you're not wasting resources with your code, I would say that's quite cost efficient and uh... I would say the more people working on a single code base, you run into a risk of someone within that group producing not-so-efficient code. Also, I would say deadlines play a big part in it and this whole cost efficiency thing, when you're sort of approaching deadlines, you're more inclined to write sloppier code that is not performing as good as it could. So, I would say the less you use your resources, the more cost efficient you'll be and that really just depends how efficient your code is and how well your infrastructure is configured.

Gregory: OK, yeah, fair answer. One last question, regarding– or maybe two more...

Edvin: Yeah two more.

Gregory: ...on my end, but because you mentioned that it's a– the only– the only true way to test serverless applications is through seeing how it behaves in the cloud. How would you ensure that the testing environment is optimized for cost efficiency while still being, I guess, like representative of the production environment? And can you even ensure this; that the testing environment is cost efficient itself?

Participant: I would say this really comes from constant iterations and the environment like it's very hard to know from the get go: “This is the most cost efficient thing we will ever have”. It mostly comes from iterative deployments of your application. Like through every deployment you will know what's bringing the application down. Like what–what are the fallbacks you're currently facing? Like if there's a specific part of the code that is not performing as well as it should, I guess through iterations you will come to that cost efficient environment you're looking for. And I guess once you reach that environment during testing, it's not that hard to recreate it during production.

Gregory: Would you say then that one of the performance metrics for cost efficiency of a serverless of testing of a serverless system is like the maturity of the organization though? Based off of what you said?

Participant: I would say so, yes.

Gregory: All right. Last question before I wrap up my question. I guess do you know of any emerging trends or technologies maybe, that may affect cost effectiveness of serverless testing? In both goods or bad way–, good or bad ways.

Edvin: It's fine if you don't know anything, it's a lot more like a bonus question.

Gregory: Yeah!

Participant: Well I would say that affects serverless testing, but it affects the serverless technologies in general I would say on AWS, constantly new generations of processors are being developed that are a lot more cost efficient than, for instance the Intel and AMD processors that a lot of people use now. I think their line of processors are called Graviton and uhm... yeah, just overall improvements in underlying hardware that is being used on these cloud providers that can bring down cost, I would say.

Gregory: Okay, cool. Good to know. Yeah, I'm good enough.

Edvin: That's the end of the interview, I believe, right?

Gregory: Yeah, thats it!

Edvin: Yeah. Well, we thank you for your time and you provided us with some really substantial data. So thank you.

Participant: Yeah, no worries.

Gregory: Thank you. Thank you.

Edvin: I'm gonna end the recording.

END OF RECORDING

A month later, a follow-up message was sent to affirm if P1 had any knowledge on Fan-in Fan-out as well as Parallelism for their enterprise. The answer provided was:

Participant: To answer it simply, we're not using fan-in fan-out for our "application". The service is split up into multiple smaller components, but the result is not aggregated in the end. Instead of fanning out, the service sort of branches out. But regarding parallel testing, we do that to an extent with our test bot. The test bot contains instructions to test every component we have and those tests can be executed in any environment we have at any time.

Participant 2

INTRODUCTIONS

Edvin: OK, I'm recording right now. Should be at least. And I also need to disable my notifications, so I don't have that in the way. Uhm... all right, all right, well, I'll just start with the first section, which is just gonna be some introduction– introduction questions so you don't have to answer like that much; you can keep your answers short. First question is how big is the enterprise that you work for?

Participant: Uhm... so presently I would say it's about 50 to 100 people depending what layer of the company we're looking at. So the immediate department, it's about 10 people. But then we do interact with other departments who are responsible for other parts of the product and their teams can vary between 10 to 20, but yeah, so yeah!

Edvin: Then the second one is, what is your development experience in years?

Participant: At this point it's about six to seven years, but yeah, it can go all the way up to 8 if we include the web development and all the other areas that I haven't been working with directly in a while, so...

Edvin: All right, what about your testing experience in years?

Participant: About four, if we're talking about– what do you mean by testing? So specifically we're all focused on testing or do you also mean testing as part of the development process? I just assume like developing tests for softwares like being– taking direct approach there.

Participant: Yeah okay, so that would be 6 years.

Edvin: All right. Then... do you have any issues to explain– do you have any sort of programming background? Briefly, like what have you been doing throughout your career? I guess.

Participant: Ooh, so I have about two to three years of web development experience, full stack, both front end and back end involved. Outside of that, I have database development experience. And back in the working experience, they intermixed [Participant laughs] is kind of a club, mostly because about four years of my experience was dedicated to consulting. And as consultants, yeah, we have had an opportunity to jump between different projects and different competencies. So very broad experience working with databases, back end primarily, but also some, experience with front end development which is a lesser–

Edvin: All right. What is your software development methodology or in what way does your company work?

Participant: I will describe it as Scrum band, so it's not a pure scrum nor pure agile. I would say it's a scrum band but leans more into the Kanban direction. So while we do have sprints, it is– doesn't necessarily follow with as Scrum prescribes by the book. We do have daily meetings, but sometimes they– we're, you know, we are away from being as short as possible and sometimes they dive deeper if they have a bigger problem at hand or a bigger, you know things that needs to be explored during that day. So augh... agile, definitely. Which degree which tastes of agile, it goes all over the place. But the scrum band with Kanban.

Edvin: Yeah, okay, that's good enough.

Participant: Yeah.

Edvin: So what serverless provider do you currently use?

Participant: AWS and Google Cloud. So we don't exist in one platform. We have different services deployed in either of those providers.

Edvin: Just I need to ask, Greg, I think we have a question about we ask which product, but I don't see it in the documents. I'm wondering if that's something we should–

Gregory: No, it's fine. Yeah,

Edvin: Yeah–

Gregory: No, it's fine. OK. Do you specifically? Do you use any specific services from AWS that are worth mentioning?

Participant: Oof, a lot from AWS, so from EC2 to S3 to code build cloud formation to Lambda. So we've—we use a lot from AWS. As for Google Cloud primarily database, big query and analytics that they offer.

Gregory: Okay.

Edvin: I—I— I just I wanted to with you Greg. I brought up— like, we're supposed to ask also like— I think that's the plan; but we also wanna know what are you *actually* creating, what are you doing at your enterprise?

Participant: Hmm...I would describe it as Stadia for mobile phones. Mobile gaming experiences.

Edvin: Uh, what for mobile phones? Sta—?

Participant: Stadia, like Google Stadia, but for mobile— for mobile phones and mobile games.

Gregory: Yup. Like a game streaming service... for mobile phones?

Participant: Exactly. Yes.

Gregory: Okay.

TESTING SERVERLESS

Edvin: All right, Okay. But then I guess we can move on to some more of the more bigger questions regarding testing serverless. And our first question is, what types of testing do you typically perform on a serverless application?

Participant: Hmm... Let's see, unit tests. Uhm... We don't have too many serverless functions used in it, but for the ones that we have, we try to cover them with unit tests. So—

Gregory: How do you cover them? Oh, sorry—

Participant: Oh yeah, unit tests and some integration tests, but we don't really have that many... uhm... Lambda functions that have to chain with one another. So usually unit test is enough to ensure that the behavior that we expect from a function will be what it will do, essentially

Edvin: Anything about integration testing?

Participant: There's several functions that do involve integration testing. So basically functions which have to chain a couple of other functions and then kind of wait for a response from them. There's not many, there's a couple of them. It's like less than 5% of...

Edvin: Okay then.

Participant: ...all the several functions that we use, so.

Edvin: Interesting.

Participant: Integration testing is not as much of a concern when it comes to serverless part of the product.

Gregory: Let me ask, what uhm... now I forgot my train of thought, but... uhm... when you test these serverless functions, how do you like? Do you try and replicate the cloud environment at all or do you just run them locally mostly?

Participant: Uhm... mostly, we use the emulators and local environments provided by AWS and the Google Cloud. Uhm... there are tools essentially that, yeah, allow you to deploy the functions locally or localize in the docker container and then run the tests.

Gregory: Would you say—

Participant: I guess the cases that we have, yeah...

Gregory: Would you say that this, uh, way of testing is efficient for the application you're making right now?

Participant: For our use case it's enough. We don't really have much data that passes through these serverless functions, mostly some coordinations or just simple payload or you know, receivable from databases and stuff so. It's— it's good. It's good enough. We don't really need to deploy it into the environment to ensure that they work with the localized testing we have. If necessary we will link our accounts which are connected to the environment where we can pull the data from test databases and like. So yeah, I would say yes, that's it's sufficient enough. It's...

Gregory: Sorry—

Participant: ...our use case.

Gregory: Sorry, sorry, I just have two, two more questions before we continue.

Edvin: Yeah.

Gregory: Uhm, so when have you ever... sorry I have two questions, one of them, do you, have you ever tested your functions in production, before?

Participant: No, not in production. So we have staging environment, development, staging environments and actual production. And then the production itself is also separated into like an internal production that is available across multiple teams and an actual separate— separate production which faces actual clients.

Gregory: Okay, and when you test these functions, because you mentioned that there were you had functions that call other functions, are there any specific events that are difficult to test?

Participant: I wouldn't say so because even those functions they're not really have too many dependencies. I believe it's three replies and two levels deep that we're going here, so one function... triggers two more functions and then waste the reply from both of them and then, you know, performs a sort of behavior. And because the amount of data that goes through them is not that big, yeah, it's there's not really delay considerations that have to be kept in mind. We don't need to consider how long the function has to run before it gets killed, because usually it takes... less than a second to perform it.

Edvin: All right.

Participant: Yeah. Not really.

Edvin: Okay. Shall I move on?

Gregory: Yeah.

Edvin: Yeah. Our next question is how do you test the integration between serverless functions and other services or components in the entire architecture? If you even have multiple components, but yeah.

Participant: Yeah, we do. There's the actual brunt of the product is pretty big, pretty complex and quite stateful. Uhm, and the the way the integration assesses with, usually we deploy things into depth layer of the environment, run the units and the integration tests on the stateful components, see how they interact, then deploy into staging for the second layer of tests. And yeah, assuming— right, another thing, once we deploy every step of the deployment into the actual environment, so development staging, we also have QA people who once the tests are performed, they perform regression tests... on it. So there's like a essentially a checklist of actions that they go through to validate that you know nothing went fell through at the cracks when it comes to automated testing and, at the every step of the way they have to confirm it. Once that is confirmed, we move on to the next gate, next stage and so on and so forth. So combination of automated tests deploying into the actual environment outside of the local machine and the QA...

Edvin: Alright alright—

Participant: ...with actual people. Yeah.

Edvin: Sounds good. So our next question is what are the most important problems you find when you're testing serverless applications?

Participant: Hm... hmhmhm hmm... the cost is always a bit annoying, so of course deployment into—we can deploy it into environment and test is there, but... I don't want to say the cost is too much. It's just, you know, seeing the ticket go up every time you perform the test and if something fails then you need to repeat it and redo it. It's eh... slight annoyance, more from the personal level, but you know, when it comes to the budget, these kind of costs. They don't— they're routing problems— so they're not— they're considered part of, you know, part of the core... of the process, and that they're not significant enough for us to be concerned about.

Edvin: Hm, so it's generally pretty stable then I guess, uhm...

Participant: Yeah.

Edvin: Okay, uhm... I'll move on then with uhm... if there's— are there any traditional testing approaches that you feel will be ineffective or inapplicable to testing your serverless systems?

Participant: What kind of traditional approaches do you have in mind?

Edvin: I believe we got the same question last time when we tested inter—

Gregory: Yeah, so like unit testing, there's end to end integration testing, there's a yeah, there— just to name a few. But like for instance, Spotify has little like Pyramid of like the different prioritizations of different testing you could do so. Yeah, like it used to be like a triangle where you would always do unit tests. But for serverless applications we— like the bare recommendation is at least is to have only— like to have to mostly focus on the integration of the whole system as a whole.

Participant: Yeah.

Gregory: And so yeah, it's more like wondering if you feel are— like wondering about any testing approaches that are perhaps maybe ineffective or maybe, don't work as well, in your day-to-day career, like.

Participant: Hmm... I mean I pretty much listed yeah that unit tests and integration tests are bread and butter, uhm... including QA with people who actually go in and test the system from the user facing side. So it doesn't— we're we've been using it for a while and it's been, working for us so far, I would say there's always, there's always more that can be done when it comes to the automation, so... when currently when it comes to integration tests as to deploy the the product from one stage into the other ones, so say into development and staging environments. We actually haven't automated that part yet, so you would have to. There's a bit of a manual work involved with deploying things and through each of the stages, specifically using clouds formation and code build, so I'm not sure how relevant when that would be for

testing specifically, but there's I– I feel like there's always, uh... It would always make things smoother if you would have automation or more automation involved for every step of the process. So once you perform local tests on a machine it would be nice. Once that's validated, we say automatically deploy things into one stage and then automate that process as much as possible. So I want to say like the pro, the traditional testing, the processes themselves are fine, they work, but the gluing things between them can always use more automation, in my personal experience.

Edvin: All right, I guess, Gregory, you gonna ask the nex– other questions from now?

Gregory: Yeah, No. I was wondering if you were done, if you're done with your part–

Participant: Even if there's more you want to ask specifically about that, I can say more. But that's pretty much– the processes work for us, but automating things in between could always, you know, smoothing things out. So automation and tests are work well together when they're combined together.

MEASURING & COST EFFECTIVENESS

Gregory: Okay. All right. Then to go on to the next part, then how would you define the concept of cost effectiveness within serverless testing?

Participant: Cost effectiveness in serverless testing... so yeah... ..

Gregory: Like–

Participant: Yeah, I'm trying to, hm, let me consider this.

Gregory: I can maybe throw some terms around and make things a bit,

Participant: Yeah, go ahead.

Gregory: Like technical depth, the time constraints per Sprint. I don't know what else to really think of–

Edvin: Money? *Laughs*

Gregory: Yeah, serverless provider, maybe, different functions might require different resources.

Participant: Yeah. As far as local development goes on your own machine, I mean it's good to run local tests as often as possible, so that doesn't really incur costs when it comes to the main environment. So from the cost perspective that's good to have locally configured environment which it doesn't interact with the system unless it's necessary and when it's necessary. So as much local as possible then... from the time constraints, again, see the thing is, while we do use several functions, I wouldn't say that they're the largest part of the product, so testing and validating them usually doesn't take too long. But. One of the experiences from my consulting days actually was that the client had a lot of several AS

functions but tests, certain tests would have to repeat executing the same function over and over again, and when those functions would be chained multiple layers down and depend on the, you know, starting functions. It could get out of hand pretty quickly if they have to be refired on and on and on during the testing process. Trying to like, yeah, generally several, architecture wise, you want to make it as flat as possible and not be not interact with too many other functions because yeah, test validation or even running it can. It gets, it multiplies. The more you have, the more layers you have interacting with one layer.

Gregory: Mhm, So make it stateless?

Participant: Make it stateless, make it as flat as possible. And if you do, use some dependencies. Perhaps, you don't want to read or change the functions directly with one another, but use some sort of a middle layer, which caches or preserves the results from other functions. So if there's some states that are shared or states that, ehm you know, are not dependent per each request, uhm, that is the states they won't change per each request caching, uhm Redis and similar ways of caching and storing things in the real time database.

Gregory: Okay. So would you say then that it would make so based on what you just said? Because this kind of goes into the other question I was gonna ask just to summarize what you just said: serverless functions should be stateless and you should make a local testing environment in order to not incur costs.

Participant: Yeah.

Gregory: Yeah, and so unit testing should also be of– Unit and integration testing should be of high importance because they're, like you said, bread and butter and– okay okay, I'm with you. In that case then, would you say that because– because you did mention that you have two serverless providers, you had like Azure– oh no, sorry, not Azure. You had Google Cloud and you had AWS and from what I remember, you use Google Cloud and their stream processing pipeline, was it, big data?

Participant: Mhm.

Gregory: Yeah. And was it their database, you also mentioned?

Participant: Uh, it's Big Query, so–

Gregory: Big Query, okay. Uhm, would you say that using these two serverless providers... would you say that because you have you're integrating between two different serverless providers that it's that it might be more expensive because you have you're using these two or would

you say that–

Participant: Yeah they are they're definitely incur more costs. However, the benefits of using, say Big Query outweigh similar offerings of what... AWS has, I mean we use DynamoDB

on the AWS side and Big Query for analytics. So different use cases and they each one of these products they're good for, you know they have their own use and but yeah, I do agree that whenever you start getting involved like two environments involved with different providers having their own costs, their rates, uhm rates that they can change all of a sudden, usually informing you in advance, several months away, actually, Big– the Big Query right now are changing their rates in July, so they do inform you such changes like five to four months in advance. But yeah, then you're kind on the clock of trying to figure out how you want to optimize what you have already. Do you want to– Is there another product to get, you know, moving things to put outweigh the long term cost; of course including the labor involved in it because that's also something that is important in considerations. Sometimes you know they can– the drivers might raise the price but it might be to laborious developer, time wise to migrate things... from one provider to the other and that's something that we face at one point with a Big Query actually. So we're exploring what other products do exist and well they do offer– many products offer similar services. It would just take too long of the time from development perspective to move away. So kind of a vendor lock in, but something that we're still satisfied with.

Gregory: Okay, would you say that... because I kind of have two questions to that I'm wondering about now. Would you say that because you both you use both Google Cloud and AWS that this adds to the complexity of your unit tests because there are two different environments being done? From what I can see, like you have Google Cloud and your AWS and so, it's– not only do you have to integrate between these two vendors, you also have to integrate with your own system and it's... uh, I can imagine that– or I can at least speculate that maybe unit testing for your organization would work. Because of the fact that it doesn't incur that many costs, but would you say that if you had just used one product from the start? And I mean, I'm just pulling at straws here, but if you just pull– if you just use just one vendor that this would lead to, I don't know like, would it be better or be worse or...?

Participant: If the vendor would provide similar service as the other vendor, and they would be priced in within the same area, then definitely using the same vendor would be good. But yeah, unfortunately some vendors have bit of an edge in certain products that they offer.

Gregory: Okay.

Participant: Well, so say with AWS EC2 instances, I would say they are much.. there's many more tools and many more flexibility in how you can configure, deploy and manage them versus to what the Google Cloud offers, including price, price wise. But at the same time, the analytics tools with what the Google works and develops there, yeah, they're– they're pretty much king in the market.

Gregory: Okay. Okay! Alright, yeah okay, so that also kind of goes into those are kind of segues into the next question. So what strategies would you use to manage and reduce costs then when testing these service applications? Because yeah, like I mentioned before like or like you mentioned before, there are different serverless or cloud solutions that have different sorts of... that have different sorts of features and they fulfill certain requirements that are

needed. But would you say that like in like in your current organization, like would you say that like what strategies would use maybe propose besides this? Yeah.

Participant: Hm, yeah I mean, yeah, KPI's are everything in this regard. So if we want to know what's happening. Testing environment, not testing environment. We want to keep track of how many tests are executed, how much every single test consumes the data, how much costly it is and just keep that data pouring in as much as possible so we could actually keep track of. Are the new tests incurring too many costs? Are the modifications allow us to reduce something, increase something? Pros and cons? So first strategy of all is to establish what KPI's we want to keep track of when it comes to testing. How are we going to keep track of it, How much it will will cost for us to keep track of it. And of course then developing visualization, or using visualization tools to effectively keep track of them on a daily basis. That's... number

one I would say, uh because yeah, without knowing any of this data it's very difficult to, you know, measure any new implementations or any changes that you introduce and how effective they are.

Gregory: So, uhm another question I guess is would you say logging would be another sort of thing? Because for instance you have two different providers. So I can imagine like how– how would you find– how do you spot errors, yeah in in your current, like at work? Because its hard to observe–

Yeah so yeah so AWS it provides Cloudwatch API interface which essentially logs everything that's going on in the ecosystem. And for Lambda functions, it's yeah, we can filter out specifically by Lambda functions and then check and see how if there's any errors that happen, what is the cost of them and analyze from that point. So this. One of the benefits of deploying things out of local into staging in depth environments, is that whatever routines and tests would perform in the environment, we can actually then see and aggregate all the errors and successful tests and visualize them in one place where all the developers and the managers can see and keep track of. Uhm yeah, I mean that's what I mean by KPIs in general. So logging every single bits of information that we can have, in this case about tests and then effectively visualizing and presenting them. 'cause, I mean it's just strategically, I mean it's it's good for the developer to know what's going on generally in the system. It's good for the team to know that. And but it's also good to for the business side of things to know– business people to know it. Because then you can motivate any changes or improvements or suggestions that you want to introduce in your testing pipeline or product pipeline. It's like having the data and the data that is well presented. That's kind of the key, yeah.

Gregory: Uhm, so I'm gonna pull this a little bit. But like... uhm so how does the system actually communicate? Because for instance, you mentioned that you have different services that integrate from AWS to Google Cloud. If that's the case, then like how do you spot errors like when you communicate between the two services?

Participant: Mhm, so given that the, you know, Lambda functions, they exist when they're once they're deployed in the environment they exist. And then the environment, AWS already takes care of logging of what happens with the Lambda function itself. So what executes it? From which account? Execution council? What are the ports? So port definitions, all of those configurations is something that you

configure within the environment itself. So in our case, AWS provides the logging functionality as part of the product, but communication, otherwise, yes, we communicate over the network with the, you know, API calls.

Gregory: Okay, all right, uhm... alright and I guess just to put on the record like so, can you distill like the key test metrics you would monitor in a serverless in a serverless system?

Participant: Number of executions, number of unique addresses that execute the functions, so different AP sources on that level, how long it takes for the function to execute. So starting stamp, with a time stamp and ending time stamp. The data processed by the Lambda function: so how much data actually was received and how much data it actually returned back, wherever it needed to be forwarded. So these are the main function– the main metrics. Then of course yes, if there's some error happens, AWS keeps track of that too, and it's possible to access the status of the function. So was it successfully executed? Was there an error? And if there's an error, then it also creates a whole dump of information...

Gregory: Alright.

Participant: ...that you can parse,

Gregory: Which– out of curiosity, which vendor incurs the most cost?

Participant: Hmm...

Like, yeah, yeah. Because they're– I know you have from what I yeah, like you have more solutions on AWS than you do on Google. So yeah–

Participant: Yeah, yeah exactly. So Google is mostly analytics and AWS is the main product and all the components exist. So yeah, AWS by the virtue of that.

Gregory: So AWS is more expensive?

Participant: Yeah.

Gregory: All right. All right. All right, and then final question, or–

Edvin: There's two– there's two questions after that.

Gregory: But yeah, how do you ensure that the test environment is optimized for cost efficiency while still being representative of the production environment? Can you like ensure this?

Participant: Oh, the parity between two, that's a... that's a good question. *Laughs.* Because we have a lot of moving components that have to be synchronized how they get deployed. A lot of synchronization is done through cloud formation and code build scripts. So once when we build one of the components, say, in the system, it is also chained with a deployment script which ensures that... this– whatever we've

compiled, actually compiled correctly, there are no errors. If it passes that gate, then we deploy it through cloud formation scripts, and those cloud formation scripts are kind of responsible for taking in the binary of the component and then propagating it where it's needed. For example, a package of Lambda functions.

Gregory: Oh oh, wait, code build. So like Jenkins?

Participant: Code build, that's yeah— it's not Jenkins. Now code build is actually AWS product, so it allows you to compile the code and build it into your packages. So it's not Jenkins, but the idea is the same, it's managed, just compiling the packages and...

Gregory: Yeah.

... storing the packages, packages, docker containers and you know the different that. So compiling part of the parts of the ecosystem and cloud formation then for deploying, scaling and ensuring the parity.

Gregory: Okay.

Participant: So say the function, the Lambda function that gets deployed. It's not switched off immediately into development, staging or production. Two functions actually exist at the same time for, you know, some period of time, and then progressively all of the nodes that we run and that depend on that Lambda function, they switch off to the next function.

If there's some errors that happen along the way, then they flip back to the previous version, do a rollback, which is not always perfect. *Laughs.* But, uh, that's I would say that's something that AWS also help— helpful with because all of these steps and configurations is something that they provide as part of their product. You just need to essentially create the scripts, configure it and yeah it will work most of the time, not always.

Gregory: So would you say that for for improving cost efficiency of— uh, of the tests of like the... test within your serverless system that the infrastructure is also really important as well as like—

Participant: Yeah, infrastructure, yeah, infrastructure, automation. So looking at your system as a whole and then like, thinking through the strategy of what depends on what. If there's some code dependencies, then yeah, you need to really think through which— what is the order of the components that you want to deploy and then if, it's testing components, production components, you know, system components in general, like what is the order that you deploy and if there's some how do you test it once you deploy, does it work, does it not? And how do you pull it out if something is wrong and, you know, roll back the whole process so that you wouldn't have a situation where you have newer components that— then some components that they're newer and depend on, you know, also other new components. But for some reason the other components got were not deployed correctly. There was some sort of an error. How do we revert all of this change without actually interrupting... things?

Gregory: Okay. Yeah, alright. Uhm..

Edvin: Last question, yeah?

Gregory: Well, I've gotten one quick one, but I don't know how much time you have left.

Participant: That's good!

Gregory: All right, good. Would you also say like organizational maturity might be one of it, because I mean you also mentioned— because from what I remember you also mentioned that you were looking at the different solutions and you were researching these different things. So wondering if that maybe ties in?

Participant: Organizational maturity? Sure. So if we're given time to explore different products, if that time is something that we can allocate, within the current Sprint? Yeah, there's some dependencies of organization, but also product maturity too. So if you have a product that starts off just from scratch, there's going to be more costs involved with, you know, experiments that would event— you would eventually have to perform. So you can, you know, when it comes to devising the plan of what kind of software, what kind of modules, how you're going to build the software, it's in an— in an agile environment, it's not something that you can do as much, it's not something that is encouraged. We want to perform things as iteratively as possible, so if the organization is mature enough to support agile working... process in the sense that there's enough budget, the management is aligned with the goals of what they want to eventually— where they want to steer the product to... Then, yeah, organizations it comes into mind, but, also if if you have a mature product, things are going to be more settled already just by the virtue of how much time was spent on the, you know, devising the architecture, setting up the infrastructure, automation, you know all of those things. So you can expect the costs essentially to be higher or much higher at the very start of the project especially in an agile environment because they're just such a big flux and... so many directions where, you know, the product can go, but as the product matures more and more the just you know the price, the cost, testing, running the product, it will decrease in the sense that you don't have to experiment or try out different directions that might not not always work out. Uhm, you might have another problem that of course you have to you need to refactor the product if you get too much technical depth. But I would say yeah, the beginning the less mature the product is, the more, in practice, the more cost there will be.

Edvin: Alright.

Gregory: Sounds good. Do you— last question, do you have any— do you might know of any emerging trends or technologies and service testing that may impact cost effectiveness?

Participant: Hmm, something new? I'm afraid not.

Edvin: Ah that's fine.

Participant: Please... know that I'm aware of from AWS side of things...hmm, nah nothing new that comes to mind. At least when it comes to traditional methods, how it is done, there's more exciting, you know, exciting developments and the AI and other stuff and how that that needs to be tested and deployed. But yeah, I don't think that's that's not really serverless.

Edvin: Yeah. All right. I guess are we done with the interview?

Gregory: I'm good.

Edvin: Then I can stop the recording. I'm stopping it right...

END OF RECORDING.

Participant 3

INTRODUCTIONS

Edvin: Like that, okay, we're now recording. And so, yeah, First off, we're gonna have some introduction questions. They're gonna be quite short, so don't worry about giving us a detailed answer. So first question is, how big is the enterprise that you work for?

Participant: Well, currently we're five people in the company. We have three people based in Gothenburg, one in Stockholm and one in Halmstad and one in Malmö.

Edvin: That's a very small company.

Participant: Yeah.

Edvin: Right, okay, what is your development experience in years?

Participant: So my development experience in both terms of work and also in personal projects is over... about 13 years now, 12 years maybe. In the industry as working with development and software engineering, it's closer to five to seven years.

Edvin: All right. And then what is your testing experience in years?

Participant: Uhm... do you mean unit testing or do you mean more user given testing?

Edvin: Like, generally like, unit testing, integration, all that, like creating such.

Participant: So that became more relevant when I started working as a software engineer, and that was so... roughly, five to seven years there?

Edvin: Okay. And briefly, what is your programming background? Like, what have you been doing through your career?

Participant: Oh, that's uh, that's a lot of things. I've been around writing basic tools for myself. I've done some development in games. I've created programming languages for myself to speed up my own work. But most of the work that I've done is as a full-stack engineer, so both back and front and the communication in between. Right now, I'm a lot focused on server infrastructure and the architecture that we have in our enterprise.

Edvin: Okay, what is your software development methodology, or in what way does your enterprise work?

Participant: So we go with the agile workflow. We have our sprints usually two weeks in between, and we do our product planning in, well, in a tool we use. We used to use ERA, but we now switched to something else that we're testing. Does that answer your question?

Edvin: Yeah, yeah. What serverless provider or providers do you currently use in your company?

Participant: We are currently using Azure for our serverless functions, but we are investigating... uh ... there are a lot of new serverless features. We actually, we are using Vercel as well for certain serverless computations as well, but that's more lightweight computations basically.

Edvin: All right. All right but those are the introduction questions. We're gonna move out to like, actually testing serverless and stuff like that.

TESTING SERVERLESS

Edvin: Uhm, so we're gonna first ask, what types of testing do you typically perform on a serverless application? On your...

Participant: So since serverless in a more like computation sense is something that we used recently started doing, right now we are benchmarking the performance we get when you bear- when we tune the parameters, such as how many workers that each instance runs at a time, or how many threads that each language worker can use. So we've done a lot of testing around that and see how many instances and how basically ho-how long the whole computation takes. So we are tracking the result of each of our serverless function, uh, parts. And I should mention we are currently using Durable Functions, which is basically orchestrations or coordinator functions that use the fan-out and fan-in strategy. So we are tracking each part of that fan-out fan-in strategy to see the result of each of the functions, and then we can figure out

how many invocations we get per second and how many, uh, basically the performance in that sense. We're also monitoring memory usage and CPU usage to make sure that we can use everything in the serverless environment that we have. And then we're using a monitoring tool that lets us see all of this pretty good. It was developed by Microsoft called the Azure Functions Monitor or Durable Functions Monitor. I think it's called.

Edvin: All right all right. Okay. Moving on then with one of the most, in no, sorry, how do you test integration between serverless functions and other services or components in the entire architecture if you even have multiple components that are, so-

Participant: Do you mean like for example communication with a database... from the serverless function?

Edvin: Like that, as well as, like, if you have multiple components that are both using serverless and how to sort of make sure they're communicating with each other. This is especially relevant if you're having multiple providers, which I don't think you did.

Participant: So I'm assuming you don't mean communicating between serverless invocations in the same environment, for example, the durable functions, the whole point of that is to communicate between a lot of functions together, because using a lot of them in parallel is much better than using one. Uhm...but so if you mean externally, right now we are not doing any communication to external providers. They're all isolated to themselves except for like database access.

Edvin: Okay.

Participant: But that is all built into the cloud infrastructure. So we just give it the credentials and then it's in the same datacenter, basically.

Edvin: Yeah. All right. I think that's a good enough answer for that question. So I'll move on with uh... what are the most important problems you find when you're testing serverless applications?

Participant: The biggest problem is figuring out what parameters to use to ensure the maximum concurrency of your functions. Because if you write your program once and then you tune it according to the memory usage and resources you have, that, for example increasing the amount of workers, language workers, or the amount of threads, then you're basically tuning it for that specific piece of code. If you then modify your piece of code to maybe use more memory than before, then you're suddenly forced to retune it the same way you did before. And there's no automated way to do this at the moment, at least in the Azure infrastructure. Uhm, so then the challenging part, and also the most time-consuming part, is to tune those values, basically, because if you tune them too high, your instances will fail because they're running out of memory. And I'm not sure if this is because Azure's function infrastructure is a little bit behind Amazon's AWS Lambda, but that is the experience that we have right now using Azure's functions, the durable functions.

Edvin: Okay... uhm, are there any traditional testing approaches that you feel are ineffective and not applicable to testing serverless systems?

Participant: Definitely not, because since each part of our pipeline in this durable functions environment is isolated and does one specific task and they're also most of the time deterministic, or some parts of it has to be deterministic, it's very easy to test like one part of it once and then do that in unit testing traditionally locally on your computer. And then you can, if one part of it works, all of those parts work. Because I mentioned before, we have the fan-out strategy that creates millions of instances doing one simple task. If you know for sure that one of those invocations will work because you've written unit tests for that part, then you pretty much know that all of them will work.

Edvin: Okay

Participant: Of course, performance will vary because you have different instances and different machines that they run on, and you don't really have control over that. That's kind of the purpose of the unmanaged serverless infrastructure. So while the performance unit tests will probably not be very giving, you can at least do testing for correctness and integrity.

Edvin: Okay, okay. I just also realized maybe you guys already talked about it before, but I forgot one of the introduction questions. So that is simply like, what exactly is your company creating? Like what product are you doing?

Participant: Yeah, I can quickly describe it again. So it's a collaborative platform in the cloud for content creators, TV producers and also cinema producers. We're also in the gaming industry for cinematics. We're working with some different companies there; and basically it allows them to internally review their own material between different departments in their organization. And they can do that using the very intuitive and easy to understand the interface. You look at the video, you can draw on it and leave comments and then we have some unique features that allows you to do all of this in real time. So you can have joint review sessions together with your team and you can all look at the same picture at the same time. So everything is synchronized and you can draw everything and you can see everything that is being done live. That is one part of it. The other part of the organization, which is the different product, but it's merged basically. And that's the live streaming... which- it differs from the traditional live streaming in the sense that it's real time streaming, so it's sub second latency up to 4K. So that allows you to edit and basically sit together with someone for example in color grading or game development, game designing or used as simple as you sharing your screen in less than a second latency, uhm, across the world basically. We've had cases where even this is used out on the field where you mount a camera on top of the car and then you can see it the other side of the world and tell them what way to drive, basically.

Edvin: Okay. All right, that's good. I realized we need to ask that within the recording as well. Okay. Well, in that case, I think Gregory, are you gonna move on with the other questions in measuring?

MEASURING & COST EFFECTIVENESS

Gregory: Yeah, sure, okay. So how would you define the concept of cost effectiveness within service testing?

Participant: Uhm, well, basically it's you pay for what you use. So instead of having a machine running 24/7 basically not doing anything during the night, you want to only pay for what you're using. So cost effectiveness is that you only pay when you tell it to do stuff. And that's kind of the goal where we have it. And also the fact that you can parallelize everything means that it is super fast and time is also money. Because if you take an hour transcoding a video using a traditional transcoder, then you're that takes a lot of time of course. And if you can do that in 5 minutes using a parallel pipeline, then that's more cost effectiveness because cost effectiveness is a... is a, combination of cost and time basically in my definition.

Gregory: Okay, fair, fair. Uhm, can you provide an example of a situation where you identify any cost inefficiencies in testing and how you addressed it?

Participant: Yeah, exactly as I said, transcoding. We are currently using a transcoding pipeline which is a managed service on Azure. It is... it is a traditional transcode. We are currently looking into a way of doing this transcoding all in serverless using a parallel transcoding pipeline. So you're splitting up the video in chunks and then you're transcoding each of the chunk in parallel at the same time, and then you merge all the chunks together at the end.

Gregory: Okay, because you mentioned the fan in and fan out strategy—

Participant: Yeah.

Gregory: —and where you split ... uh... one big task into smaller lam- into smaller serverless functions. Would you say that boosts the cost effectiveness of the platform? Or would you say, because uh... I'm only just grasping at straws here, but wouldn't it uh... Would you also be susceptible to a lot of cold starts or how does it actually work?

Participant: So if the alternative is to do all of the chunks. So in the example of the transcoding, if the alternative is to do the transcoding in a sequence using a single machine, you're still paying for the entire uptime of that machine during the course of the transcoding. If you instead can do all of that in parallel, even if some of them have cold starts, you're still: say that a chunk takes one second, and you're doing a one hour long video, then it's going to take 60 seconds for a traditional transcoder, but it might take 3 seconds for a parallel one, including the cold starts of two seconds if there is one. So you're still reducing the delay from 60 seconds to three seconds because the cold starts are individual per instance, which is a group of invocations. So if it needs to create a new instance then it doesn't have to wait for the previous instances if it has to create all of them. So you can just do that at the same time.

Gregory: So overall, does it cost more to split them into smaller functions, or does it cost less?

Participant: It costs less because running a function a small task is cheap because you're paying for the duration of the function. If you have a function that doesn't do much but it takes a long- it- it doesn't do, it takes a long time to do, but it does the same work as a function that does little or takes a short time. You're paying for the amount of CPU time that your- that your invocation takes, so splitting up the task into different serverless functions means you have less time for each instance and they can be done in parallel. Usually, from what I've seen is splitting it up can actually be faster than doing them in sequence because of context switching.

Gregory: When you when you test these functions, how exactly do you test them? Like, do you do you test them? Do you test them locally? If you test them locally, then in that case how do you replicate the production environment?

Participant: So the only way to test them locally is to have a machine that is capable of doing all of this in parallel. I recently got myself a Ryzen 7950X [CPU] with 32 logical cores, so I can do 32. Invocations at the same time.

That's nowhere near enough to do the same kind of production environment that we have, sending out tasks for millions of invocations. So you can only do this locally when you're doing small tasks, or at least small parallel tasks. So testing it locally is hard, meaning you have to get tools that lets you monitor your invocations on the cloud in the production environments. But what we usually do is we use to set up a production environment and then a development environment that are identical basically. And then we do all of our testing on the development environment.

Gregory: And because you also mentioned that you split these into multiple, uhm, into smaller functions, is it difficult to monitor the, like is it difficult with observability and monitoring and metrics. Like if an error happens on one smaller function, does it? Like does it take a lot of time to debug?

Participant: So as I mentioned before, we track the result of all of our small parts. Like every invocation we track the result of. Both in terms of progress and also in terms of if it succeeds or not. Eventual errors that is stored in a database and you can do a simple query to get any invocation that resulted in an error. It can be difficult to debug when an actual invocation starts because of cold starts, or because the orchestrator is not, because in terms of durable functions, the orchestrator can kill itself while it's waiting for the invocations to start up, basically.

Gregory: Okay.

Participant: So, uhm, that can be sometimes hard to debug, like the timing to start- to start the invocations up. But usually tracking the result of something is very easy. That's just a simple database query.

Gregory: So just to clarify this, so it's on the record, kind of. When you test these serverless functions, you test them in production. Was it or?

Participant: Well, it's an environment simi- identical to the production environment.

Gregory: Okay.

Participant: We don't do the testing on the production environment.

Gregory: Yeah, yeah.

Participant: But we, but our goal is to have the exact same infrastructure in all of our coworkers... uhm... development environments as the production environments, because we want to avoid any kind of differences.

So when we're testing things locally, sure we sometimes use the emulator, but if we're gonna submit a task that is large for testing. We need to do that on a production like environment in the cloud. So we do have two services that are identical, one for the production and one for the development and we also have one for staging of course. So we have three really.

Gregory: Okay. And then, I've got three more questions. One of them, do you mind saying again on the record, because I know you mentioned this a couple times, but do you mind giving a quick bullet point, of like what strategies you'd use to manage and reduce costs when you're testing serverless applications.

Participant: So the strategy we usually do with the serverless now that is still something that we-we... well for starters, we are migrating some of our services from traditional service servers like virtual machines to serverless. That is one cost effective measure we can do, because if we have a virtual machine running 24/7 doing nothing, we're paying for nothing.

Gregory: Yeah.

Participant: So that is one measure. And when it comes to actually the actual serverless environment, we try to tune it to do as much as possible in the shortest amount of time. That's really the— more parallelism means faster, and you have to kind of weigh cost of having a lot of invocations compared to the gain you get in time. But usually the cost per invocation is very cheap and that's like you're supposed to kind of do a lot of things at once.

Gregory: OK, so when it comes to testing... the serverless applications, what sorts of metrics do you usually look for? To minimize cost of course.

Participant: Of course we look at the amount of code starts, we look at the amount of invocations that we start up. We look at the memory— like the utilization of each instance. Now, the instance is not something you manage yourself, but you can still affect its usage. If you have an instance that is capable of running 100 invocations, but you only have 10 because you've limited it to 10 per instance, then obviously you're wasting that instance capability and if you can maximize the efficiency of the— so it's important to understand how the serverless environment works. Because it's not just as simple as telling it to do thousands of invocations. Because if you do it naively and you just do the default configuration, you can run into memory consumption problems that you might use

too much, or you might use too little because you're not tuning it to your own code. So it's important know what's happening in the background, and Azure has some pretty— if you read it like 10 times, you're gonna have a good time, but if you read it once, you're not gonna understand much. That's the experience I've had from their documentation. But how the instances are scaling, how the language— the programming language is run on each of the instances is important because, for example, if you're using Python, you're per default limited to a single worker at a time. If you're using .net, you have more. If you're using JavaScript, you have more. It depends on the language you're using. That's also something you have to consider. What language will you use and what kind of configuration do I need to do to maximize that language?

Gregory: Okay, because you mentioned also that you need to know what's happening in the background at all times when you have, because you also mentioned that you use certain— that— that you use an environment that's similar to production, that is simulated. Like, it's emulated to run just like production.

Participant: Well, it's an identical setup in the cloud. I mean, we do have an emulator when doing things, small things locally on your computer, but we can't emulate the production environment, so we just have literally an identical set-up for like private use, so it's not emulated. We have the production environment and then we have the development environment, but they're functionally identical. They have the same restrictions, they have the same parameters, same configuration. Well, unless we change them of course in development one for testing. But the only way to test performance, at least so far for us, has been to have an identical setup for both production and development.

Gregory: Okay. All right. In that case, my last question is, do you know of any emerging trends with tech that in serverless testing that may impact cost effectiveness?

Participant: Uhm... well... I've seen— I've seen at least, I don't know if it's a trend, but I've seen a lot of recommendations of splitting up— so there's something— yeah, this can be very specific to Azure, but I'm not sure. You can maximize your performance by splitting up your coordinator or your orchestrator into sub orchestrators because then they read from different partitions in the storage that they use to monitor the status of the invocations. That's— now— now it's like very low level understanding of the serverless that I haven't really delved into. But I've seen that... people do recommend if you want the maximum performance, is to actually consider what's the orchestrator and stuff— and when I'm speaking, this is all in terms of durable functions. That's the only thing we're using right now for this.

Gregory: A—a—and just to kinda to make sure durable functions is like, it's— it's like is it a specific Azure, an Azure function terminology?

Participant: Yeah I think it is and it basically means that you have, you can have scheduled

functions, you can have orchestrator functions, activity functions or basically like yeah– it basically is...is their way of segmenting of the entire like fan out fan in strategy, basically. You have the functions which is in control of handling all of the invocations that you want to use, and you can split those up into smaller orchestrators because then they will read from different partitions, which is faster because they have an internal queue system kind of thing that they reach from. And that's– I don't know– it's probably not a trend, but it– it seems at least on Microsoft's side, that if you want the most performance, you need to tune your variable and test your variables to match their internal systems. So I wish there was some kind of automated trend or automated way of tuning your algorithm to the amount of– or to the variables that the infrastructure has. But right now, that's not something I've found.

Gregory: Yeah, I think that's– that concludes the interview for me. Do you have anything Ed?

Edvin: No. I think this is great.

Gregory: All right.

Participant: Yeah. So, I mean, feel free to reach out late– I mean, we are looking to find better ways of doing this, I mean right now we're using Azure, but we are looking at how this would be handled on AWS, because we know AWS is ahead with this. Maybe they have a lot of better tools, but from Microsoft's side, this is the status that we've found right now and it's quite new on Azure too.

After a few minutes of discussing something the participant preferred to keep out of the interview.

Edvin: I guess I haven't ended the recording yet. Shall I stop the recording officially so we can say that the interview is done or?

Participant: Yeah, sure.

Gregory: Yeah.

Participant: Yeah.

Edvin: Yeah

END OF RECORDING.

Participant 4

Did not consent to being recorded to allow for an easier discussion.

The following notes were documented during the interview.

INTRODUCTIONS

1. How big is the enterprise that you work for?

- Small, a bit over 20 employees

2. What is your development experience in years?

- 27 years

3. What is your testing experience in years?

- 10 years on and off. Not major part of work. In recent years it has not been too much, and mostly because of the way our set up. What he does in his daily life at the company is that they work a lot towards their production system and our customers most often don't have separate testing environments and given that context there is not much room for structured testing. In the early days he did Unit testing.

4. What is your programming background?

- Most in java
- 80% of my time
- Javascript typescript html

5. What is your software development methodology?

- Lack of industry definition for what they do.
- Described it as weekly standups.

6. What serverless provider(s) do you currently use in your enterprise?

- AWS

7. Tell us about your product that has serverless components.

- PaaS, serverless solutions for certain functionalities
- Structure where we have a Java backend but we integrate it with serverless for some tasks
- We provide a platform + toolset for simplifying business to business transactions (eCommerce)

TESTING SERVERLESS

8. What types of testing do you typically perform on serverless applications?

- Because of the structure of the product and the way we use serverless, we have some functions within the system where we use AWS lambda for some tasks, so what we typically do is when we set up such a function up we create a couple of unit tests to ensure that it does what it needs to do

- I would say that's pretty much it, we most often have within the function some kind of notification or logging so that some things are exposed
- In our context this is one of the benefits of having serverless, we have between 150-200 customers where most of them run on systems on premises, so if something breaks in their premises, we would have to potentially update a bunch of unique solutions
- If something breaks in lambda, it will probably break for everyone, but the fix would be for everyone, and because everyone runs in the same place, that error or that bug then showing itself is so much higher within the serverless context.
- Serverless can make it possible for you in some cases to not be as detailed in your testing in that context because it's often small components where you can often employ integration testing, where you just really have to care about that it works as it should, and then you can fix it quite easily because of how small and modular it is
- It is not as bad to find a bug in production and thus you don't need to have as much detailed knowledge of the tests.
- One thing that I think is very important and when you come from a non serverless background, is the importance for execution time, not only for the testing itself, but for the lambda function, because if you have something that you run and if you do something that affects the execution time badly
- HTML file to a PDF -> gathers resources to a product catalog, one thing we have experienced is that if that document contains references to images that reside on a really slow server, that could cause execution time for that lambda function to go from the expected sub second to fifteen minutes instead.
- Finding that kind of problem is so much more important in a serverless context because if that kind of problem gets out to production, it could really drive costs really fast because it is paid per execution.
- Response time is extremely important in lambda functions
- We use Amazon and we get notifications about cost going away, so we would know if a lambda function starts to behave slowly and therefore incur costs

Note: Question 9 and 10 were skipped due to the first one being irrelevant, and the other was answered in the participant's tangent.

11. Are there traditional testing approaches that you feel are ineffective or inapplicable to testing serverless systems?

- No detailed integration tests
- There are some things that are important that historically haven't been in the same way
- Oh, it works, nice nice nice
 - It could incur a lot of costs
 - Monolithic backend that interacts with one serverless function upon another, simple setup so no issues were really experienced
 - Keeping track of execution time is important!
 - When you move to a context where you pay for a provider for execution time, small differences of execution time would drive costs

MEASURING & COST EFFECTIVENESS

12. How would you define the concept of cost effectiveness within serverless testing?

- Not wasting time

13. Can you provide an example of a situation where you identified a cost inefficiency in testing and how you addressed it?

- Image problem
- When it comes to the solution to that, we actually applied a rule in those documents, we require that all external resources are fetched from Cloudfront in Amazon where we know they can work with most efficiency, and we add it to system logging for more info
- We move to centralised logging system, so that we would know about it, by using the external logging tool we are able to aggregate all situations and find those issues more expediently
- Centralized logging is important for:
 - I have mostly experience in AWS, but Cloudwatch
 - It could be really important because if you have logging and you are able to get information from those logs, you are able to fix errors and be aware of errors that happen in the actual application in production that are able to be resolved
 - You can then be lighter on the testing beforehand because in general, this is my approach to testing but you don't need to spend time testing things that isn't a big issue if they happened. In my opinion, you should only spend a lot of effort testing stuff where the cost of the consequence is more than the cost of finding it
 - You learn in school that you should test like this, but that really depends on the situation, if you sell a system that millions of people will use and install, finding bugs is really important beforehand
 - If you sell a system where you do a lot of customisations for each customer, and you do this in close collaboration with the customer, then it does not make sense to test things that maybe just a few people will use. If they find it then they will tell you and they will then in turn talk about it

14. What strategies would you use to manage and reduce costs for serverless systems?

- Don't do it if you don't need to

Follow-up: If you could redesign your product from the start, how would you do?

- No good answer
- Jokingly replied the application I have is perfect in every way

15. What are the key test metrics you monitor in a serverless system?

- Response time
- We measure what happens ad-hoc, but those metrics are not in the context of testing, we just measure the entire product ad hoc.

16. How do you ensure that the testing environment is optimized for cost efficiency while still being representative of the production environment? Can you even ensure this?

- We only do serverless part of testing, in our context we just use for parts of the system

17. Do you know of any emerging trends or technologies in serverless testing that may impact cost effectiveness?

- Interested in how we could leverage event driven architectures but I don't have concrete examples
- Using serverless to make our application more loosely coupled and besides the way we use serverless now, which is being able to manage heavy workloads for short periods of time, the other upside is to decouple the application and make other parts
- Even if it is quite small parts that are being used with serverless right now, they are still the easiest parts to maintain and very little issues regardless
- For that reason I think being able to move a large portion of the application into that context would be beneficial.
- They accept that we can deliver a solution cheaply that could contain bugs

Participant 5

INTRODUCTIONS

Edvin: Ok, recording is now ongoing. So we're gonna start off with some basic introduction questions so you don't have to be, you don't have to— You can give quick or short answers if you need, if you want to. So the first one is; how big is the enterprise that you work for?

Participant: 55 employees.

Edvin: 55. Ok, what is your development experience in years?

Participant: Uh... 30?

Edvin: 30? Ok, damn. What is your—

Participant: Okay, okay, okay— let me redact that one. It's actually more like 25 if we're counting like working years.

Edvin: Yeah, okay—

Participant: Go with 25!

Edvin: Yeah. So to follow up on that, what is your testing experience in years? As in like mainly creating tests and being involved with them?

Participant: Yeah, uhm... about a decade of doing that.

Edvin: Okay. Then, you can briefly describe what is your programming background; so what have you been up to?

Participant: Yeah, okay... low level program– client side development, let's put it that way, primarily. Yeah. So that's low level up until building like application front ends and working with people that develop large scale back end systems.

Edvin: Mhm, what is your software development methodology A.K.A in what way does your enterprise work?

Participant: Eh, Agile.

Edvin: That's a fair answer. Not a lot of people seem to know. Like everyone says agile and that's kind of what we expect. Uhm, what serverless provider do you currently use in your enterprise?

Participant: Google cloud.

Edvin: Yeah, google cloud– is it called Google Cloud Services in its full name?

Participant: It's I think– In that case, they rebranded recently because typically we refer it as GCP, Google Cloud Platform.

Edvin: Okay. Cuz we've had people say different types of google–

Participant: Nope, it's gotta be Google Cloud Platform.

Edvin: Okay. So, last question regarding introductions is for you to tell us about the current product that is using serverless components.

Participant: Current product is... Let's pick. Uhm... It's a service that collects performance– collects application specific performance metrics and then presents it back to the developers, in like in a relevant format.

Edvin: Mhm, so...

Participant: Do you want more detail?

Edvin: Yeah, yeah, you can give us a little bit more detail.

Participant: All right. Okay. So imagine that you are... you're building a bunch of levels for your game. And one problem that you have is that when content creators construct these levels; it– like they don't always have the right tools to measure what's the actual like performance of this when it's at runtime. And this gets worse when you're scheduled all across Sweden and you're developing a game for PC, where everybody is on a different pc. Okay, so now it's getting a little bit hairy here. So– and– so what you would like is to get some kind of reliable baseline. Some kind of repeatable tests for this, but how do you do that if it's not about “call this function over here”, but it's rather a bunch of artists or modifying the layout of a world, how do you measure the performance of a world? So, what we've done is we create a

system where the artists themselves, they can play, they can drop a bunch of camera locations around the world. *Participant makes a pop sound.* So let's say on like a 200 by 200 meters sized map, they're going to drop maybe 100 camera locations there. And then we written automation that runs on one specific pc in one specific server room, and on every like every night it grabs latest. And then it runs a script where it teleports from camera location to camera location, hangs around for half a second.

Edvin: And measures performance, right?

Participant: Yes. So it does that through all these 100 locations. And that's nice. But the next problem then is how do we make this data accessible? That's where the serverless tech comes in. So the script then posts these metrics to a back end and that's where we have a cloud function that is like the simplest way for us to get a rest api that is available 24/7. So that's when it's going to receive that, then stuff the results into google's cloud fire store, which is a database that we're gradually moving away from using all together. It's fantastic for doing proof of concepts, but as long as you want to do any kind of queries, you run into limitations and it's just not built for that. But anyway, so there we have parts of it. Now— okay so. In addition to that, how do we present these results in a way that makes sense? Well, okay. So we built the web front and that then talks to Cloud Firestore, so you can browse the different results there. And in addition to that: We have another piece of logic which goes, talk directly to the APIs, pull out the numbers from there, pull out yesterday's numbers, pull out today's numbers, do a diff. And sort them, figure out which were like— so go like— okay, how did the mean and average performance change? Did it go up or down by percent? And like, which were the 10 slowest of these camera locations? Sometimes there's one camera. So you can see like— by having this set up and having the surrounding and having posting to them every night means that given time, given that they're actually interested in this, they themselves make the level render at six milliseconds max on Geforce 1080 ti. And you don't need someone going around like the person— the person like the engineer, extreme technical artist is going around cracking the whip and going like— going “okay” and you know like that person needs to do that every week. In that case, because artists will continuously refine, refine, refine, refine. And if they don't know what makes it go up, if they don't have that, if they don't have that regulation built in, then some human will need to be there to close the loop.

Edvin: Okay.

Gregory: All right.

Edvin: So does that mean, is this strictly game development?

Participant: Yes.

Edvin: Okay.

Participant: Well, game development and architecture visualization.

TESTING SERVERLESS

Edvin: Yeah. Okay, that's a very nice and detailed answer. Very nice, thank you. But that means we're gonna move on to some more, I guess, more technical questions regarding testing serverless. So the first one we usually ask is what types of testing do you typically perform on the serverless application?

Participant: Ehm... we do unit tests on the s– internal logic. We typically do a couple of API tests as well and then there's manual user testing.

Edvin: Uhm...

Participant: So that's like full integration tests. The last point.

Edvin: Okay, I was thinking about a follow up regarding integration if you would– If you would like to think broadly regarding unit versus integration testing, would you say that you have more than one or the other?

Participant: I would say that we lean a lot more heavily towards integration testing than unit tests. And the reason for this is that there typically isn't a lot to unit test within the serverless functions. They're glue logic. So if we just look at “where do the problems show up?” and you think it takes time to develop and maintain tests, so there's that cost, but then you get the value of the test coverage that from that cost benefit analysis the 1st place like when we're developing something from 0 using serverless tech, the types of things where we are going to use serverless tech, then generally speaking you find that– We get the most value from doing integration tests in the form of API tests. Then if whatever is in the serverless logic starts getting convoluted enough, maybe... it starts becoming valuable to have unit tests in addition to these API tests.

Edvin: So just to clarify, API tests, that is a kind of integration test, yes?

Participant: Okay right. Talk to the rest apis, instead of call this– instead of call this function in a similar way. Have you ever tried to write a test for a command line application?

Edvin: Not me.

Gregory: No, I haven't, no.

Participant: So one way of doing that is... is to effectively write a couple of– write a little shell for you, that goes: “Okay, I'm going to take in three files. File 1 contains a command line and file 2 contains the expected text output, and File 3 contains some kind of fluffy specification with like stuff that isn't possible to capture just through these two files.” Like, maybe ignore this kind of thing, be lenient with this and that, and maybe make sure to have this thing running on the side when you're on the command. Like maybe sure that this actual service, say like extra configuration is like File #3. So then once you have a framework like that, then you start like doing triplets of these files, bom, bom, bom, bom, bom and suddenly you have some kind of coverage that tells you: “All right. I've been messing around inside of the bowels of these command line applications and it does not result in obvious errors when executing any of the commands.”

Gregory: Ok, ok.

Participant: And it's surprising— Like, can you— If you don't do this, then as you're working through the bowels of your application, you will randomly break subcommands. That happens every now and then. And how do you find that out? You're going to have a manual user test that? You are probably going to be the manual user. Do you ever bother running all the subcommands? No, you don't. Not when you post 3 sub commands. So that scalability problem there is a point where okay— it's in order to get that coverage... then like if you want to— if you want to have a scalable strategy there and it helps a ton to have that kind of test coverage. So then imagine that you're starting out with the command line application from scratch: you're doing your first “hello world”. Are you going to start with unit testing your hello world? Or are you going to set up this little framework to launch the hello world program?

Gregory: Have my own framework?

Participant: Yeah, it depends a little bit, probably. If you are starting— the first thing you want to do is create a couple of commands that actually work. Or if you start out with building some gnarly complicated logic, probably, that probably drives what you want to do. Am I first going to unit test my algorithm over here? Or am I first going to set up this framework to just make sure that the first two subcommands print something reasonable, and then I start hooking up an algorithm to the bowels of it? So you see like... does that kind of make sense?

Gregory: Uhm, I can see where this is going, but I'm a bit unsure as to why you use unit tests or why you prefer integration tests or unit tests. I think that's a—

Participant: We are probably gonna— we do write both. But the question is... like what I see is if it's a trivial command line application then it's not necessarily worthwhile to write a lot of unit tests. But even for a trivial command line application, it's supremely nice to have coverage that shows you that “yes, the commands are indeed working as expected”.

Gregory: Okay okay.

Participant: And then, depending on how complex the internals of the thing gets, that's more and more motivation to write more and more unit tests.

Gregory: Okay okay.

Participant: Now imagine that. Yeah, so imagine that this command line application instead is a serverless function which exposes the rest API. Using the same line of reasoning, you could say that there's just a bunch of... there's just a bunch of stupid glue logic inside of that serverless function. That's where you start. So what do you want to know? You want to make sure that this and that and that API call returns something sensible.

Gregory: Oh, okay, okay.

Participant: So therefore– so therefore you won't have a test suit for that. And then when your glue code starts becoming more than just glue code, when it actually does a bunch of processing, when it does something nontrivial, when you're– when it starts turning in– when you start going from... when you start getting into position where i'm going to need to manually construct a shit-ton of test cases for the rest API because– Because I'm indirectly trying to provoke, like the different tests– the different code paths inside my complex logic by sending things in from the outside. When you get too many of these, you're probably going to say: Ok, you know what it gets like– I'm going to be writing like 300 different test cases here for the rest API. I can get by with just 10 for the API and a couple of unit tests.

Gregory: Oooh, okay.

Participant: And suddenly...

Gregory: Okay, okay, yeah, I see what you mean. I see what you mean though. Yeah. No. Yeah. No. Yeah, like you basically by doing integration tests, you save– You save time and money because you get the result at the end that's aggregated rather than...

Participant: Yes.

Gregory: Like, yeah, because at the end of the day, that result that's aggregated at the end of the day means that all the components or all the serverless functions that are running work in the way you would expect it to work.

Participant: Yes, and I'm probably gonna create that suit anyway.

Gregory: Yeah. Yeah.

Participant: Because either I create a suit or I sit there manually doing a bunch of card commands and look at the output.

Gregory: Okay, okay, yeah, I'm with you. I'm with you, okay.

Edvin: We can move on to the next question. Uhm... okay, so this might–, i don't know if you've kind of answered parts of it– Okay, how do you test the integration between serverless functions and other services or components in your entire architecture?

Participant: We do that by deploying it. We deploy it to Google Cloud and test that. We don't use local emulators.

Gregory: Do you have your own testing environment in google cloud?

Participant: Yes.

Gregory: Okay. So there's two environments. There's the testing and the production environments.

Participant: Yes.

Gregory: Okay, okay.

Edvin: Are we happy with that answer? Yeah, I'm happy with it. What are the most important problems you find when testing server applications? A bit of a broad question, but—

Participant: Yeah yeah, hmm... There are some problems. There are about testing—

Edvin: But specifically for serverless then.

Participant: Specific— Okay okay. So the biggest problem with serverless is that, it's typically that I need to deploy it to a bespoke, like Google Cloud specific environment. That's the number one problem using that technology. Like I can't spin up, I can't on demand spin up a replica of it on my own workstation or on a test machine somewhere else. It needs to run in Google Cloud. And that means that it's difficult to create, like eh, let's say that you want to have a test suite, and you want to have that test suite run on every pull request.

Edvin: Yeah.

Participant: What happens if two people happen to be developing on this piece of software at the same time?

Gregory: Then changes from the first user might over— or you might get merge conflicts from the second user, and there might be.

Participant: And what happens with the test environment inside of google cloud? Would anything happens when there are two pull requests have been created roughly at the same time? And then you have two github actions jobs that are attempting to deploy to slightly different versions of the serverless infrastructure to google cloud to that same test project at roughly the same time? And this then leads to github action scripts. Attempt to run test suits that hit the rest APIs inside of that same environment again.

Gregory: I'm unsure what...

Participant: The fundamental problem here is we have one test environment. Only one set of tests can be done against one test environment at the same time.

Gregory: Ok, ok.

And if you two happen to be coding at the same time, then you're going to, like, you're pretty soon going to, like, start ping ponging each other over Slack: “All right, i'm creating a pull request now. Can you

please make sure not to create a pull request yourself in the next 15 minutes?" Ok, yeah, so then ok, so then so. So what you need to do to get away from that is either trying to get some kind of like torrent style thing going in Github actions or whatever, like CIC [?], the platform you're using, or you need to be able to create multiple concurrent deployments. And if you look at— now here, what's problematic then is that a lot of the tooling for serverless is not designed to be— It's not designed to be like possible to easily parameterize.

Gregory: How so?

Participant: You— it's typically designed so that you can, like, there are unique identifiers involved here and there worldwide global things. For example, if you're using google cloud and you want the storage bucket. When you create the storage bucket in google cloud; that needs to have a global unique identifier across all of google cloud and this involves every other tenant in google cloud.

Gregory: Okay, okay, okay.

Participant: So if you want to on-demand create just for this pull request, let's deploy a unique set of serverless functions and the other required stuff. You need to make up logic which will like on-demand be able to generate a guaranteed unique identifier for that storage bucket. Yeah, yeah, like you thought the problem was with the serverless function. No, no, no. The problem is with all the other infrastructure around it.

Gregory: So, so would you say that so— so back to this example of the two people trying to send in a pull request and deploy their changes towards the same environment. If I deploy my changes towards this environment without the same identifier, there's no guarantee that the code that is actually being tested is the exact same as the other code that's being deployed right now.

Participant: Exactly. So you need— Yeah, so you like— so— the serverless stuff you need to do— put in a lot of effort to make it possible to on demand create environments. And what you're probably going to end up doing is you're not going to create unique Google Cloud projects which are [???] isolation in their model. But rather you're going to have one giant: the testing project. And then you're going to create reams of these functions and various other resources in there and rely on naming conventions. And kind of like hope that it in a sense like hoping that it works out and sooner or later you will run into one or more resources. One you start— Once you get complicated and you need a little network resource then you're okay. Then this strategy breaks down. So there are— once it gets— once it gets complicated, then this testing, these testing strategies get difficult. So what I look for when I am in more complicated scenarios, I want the ability to run these things outside of Google Cloud. And that is why we're gradually moving out to doing more things on Kubernetes, because Kubernetes provides an abstraction layer that makes it go “run this bunch of things on that machine over there”.

Gregory: But does that simulate the serverless environment? By running it on a Kuber—

Participant: No, it's... You're 50% away from serverless style at that point. Because a lot of serverless is about you don't need to— Like, I want this set of things, and I don't give a shit about how these things

actually— these things shall run. I don't give a shit about *how* they run. Make them run for me, please. That's kind of part of the premise of serverless. Kubernetes means spending a lot of time learning about how to— learning about weird things happening inside of a Kubernetes cluster, which is kind of antithetical, but serverless is worth it up until a certain point of complexity. Once these things, once it's important for you to be able to do pull requests in parallel. Once it's important for you to be able to code on the thing and run tests on it when you don't have internet available to you. Even though this is a primary internet capable service, once it's important for you to run the test suite on that box over there in a self-contained manner because you want to observe certain things that are difficult to observe, in the serverless environment. Like you want to measure, you want to perform— like fine grain performance measurements of your logic and you want to use operating system level introspection of the process that is running. You don't get these facilities from serverless like from serverless deploy— from the serverless operating environment. Once you start needing these very specialized things, then you're going outside of the limits of serverless. So a lot of this boils down to how complicated is the thing that you want to do

Gregory: Okay. But oh Ed, is it okay if I ask another question?

Edvin: *Nods.*

Gregory: Do you— But when you talk about Kubernetes and when you talk about orchestrating these, orchestrating these containers to sort of like— I didn't quite catch what you said, but I don't think i've quite caught what you said about why you're moving towards containerizing your functions.

Participant: Yeah.

Gregory: And like the actual limitations of this— of serverless, I don't think I quite caught that.

Participant: Okay, yeah, yeah, I'll see if I can give a concrete example. Yeah, okay... let's say that you two are developing on the same thing and it's a combination of... a couple of like lambda functions and then DynamoDB in the back, like, I'm guessing here that you're more familiar with AWS than Google, is that correct?

Gregory: Yeah, yeah.

Participant: All right. All right. So you have a simple update on that. You two happen to be developing on that on the same day. And as you're developing on that, sometimes you are messing around with the data inside of that— inside of the database, occasionally in your test DB. Yeah, all right, you're probably not deploying the lambda to AWS for every single test draw. Hopefully you have a way to, like, do the quicker iterations by running the code locally on your machine. All right, that's nice because then you can just with a couple of seconds turn around time. That also means that you can probably run a quick test suite that goes directly against that program of yours on your local machine. But it's just a shame that your program is probably still talking to a DynamoDB database in AWS, because it's a ton more difficult to get the DynamoDB database running locally on your machine. How do you do that, even? So, that means that you're effectively accept— You're probably accepting that you only have one DynamoDB database out there. So sometimes something is changing because Edvin did something to the database and while you

were coding on it. And after a while you go: “Maybe we're going to have the Gregory DynamoDB database and the Edwin DynamoDB database for the project. Yeah, splits it apart: okay. And then it's going to be like the global test environment DynamoDB database in there. But... Ok...? So is there– It's not so bad with DynamoDB because that was probably schema less. But if these were SQL databases where you had to migrate versions and make sure that the tables are the same, but they're not supposed to be the same all the time across this. Because, you hear how this becomes an unholy mess to manage.

Gregory: Yeah, ok. Ok. Yeah. So what I'm gathering from this is that from what you said way, way before about how you use integration tests to test the aggregates of the different functions. So it is the exact same thing when we use serverless and that the result that we get is eventually consistent. And so it's not necessarily a guarantee that when one person tests, the results will be the same as the other person's results because we don't really know. There's not enough observability in these functions to correctly determine test cases, sometimes.

Participant: Yes, correct, you need to– Yeah, like you need to make sure that only one part is doing one thing at a time, or you need multiple, like multiple replicas of the back end, like of all the back end stuff. So imagine instead with your case where you're coding your lambda function and you have DynamoDB there. Imagine if you could run the DynamoDB locally on your machine, then you would know that like. Then you would know what's going on that it's only you touching your DynamoDB. And you will find more and more examples of this for every piece of serverless tech that you use. You run into this–

Edvin: You wanna get it more local kind of, or you wanna move away from serverless as you mentioned earlier?

Participant: Yes.

Edvin: Okay, should we probably move on to the next question, cuz that's very good.

Gregory: That's really detailed, very detailed.

Edvin: Exactly. You might have also talked a little about this, but yeah, are there traditional testing approaches that you feel are ineffective or inapplicable to testing serverless systems?

Participant: *Participant thinks for 5 seconds.* Any kind of test approach that... is based around detailed inspection of the host operating system. Like the state of the entire operating system goes out the window.

Edvin: Okay. Do we need an elaboration on that?

Gregory: Yeah, sorry.

Participant: Yeah, you have a people window. Into what's going on you have this web front end. Compare that when you're sitting on the terminal and you can like list processes and check CPU usage. So a lot of like– automate– it doesn't affect automated testing so much, but like manual testing and like testing/debugging. There you are at the mercy of whatever tools this specific cloud provider offers you.

Gregory: Okay. Wait, Ed, did you catch that? I didn't quite catch that.

Edvin: Uh–

Participant: Sure. Right. Okay. So if you're wondering, you've written a bunch of logic and you have a bunch of for-loops in there and you're wondering: “Okay, am I spending a lot of time in this for-loop over there?” Okay, you could– If you can run it locally, then you can run a profiler against your piece of code, If it's running within– like within the lambda, you can't apply a profiler to it when it's over there. If you are wondering about memory usage and start wondering like a bit more detailed, like start thinking like a bit more detailed questions. Maybe you want to... dump all memory allocations.

Gregory: Yep.

Participant: You can't really do that in the lambda because where is the dump with the memory allocations going to get written? Are you going to upload that file to a storage bucket? Here its much more complicated than just running something on your local, in a terminal, and then you get file on the side which is half a GB in size because you're doing a ton of memory allocations and then you inspect this half a GB-size file with another tool that you have, on hand. But yeah, but you can't write files to this can have them persist in the lambda function and even if you could do that there would be no way through the AWS console to download that file. No, you need to upload that file to a– that cloud storage bucket and then you need to go to fetch that file from the cloud storage bucket. So you're spending like 2 hours engineering a solution just to persist the file. So you can look at that file once. And all this because you don't have control over how the cloud function is run. So it's not so much. Getting back to the question, I don't think it's so much about testing approaches being ineffective, it's more about introspection and debugging methods becoming ineffective.

Edvin: Okay. I'm going to move on, I think. *Edvin disconnects from the call.*

Edvin reconnects to the call.

Participant: That's also where you're moving on. *Laughs*

Edvin: I disconnected by accident. *Laughs.* I accidentally pressed the back button.

Gregory: Is that me?

Edvin: Yeah– what?

Gregory: No, no, no, no.

Edvin: Should I keep asking the questions, Greg?

Gregory: If you want, yeah, if you want.

MEASURING & COST EFFECTIVENESS

Edvin: I can do that. So now we're gonna get a bit more into cost effectiveness. So starting with that, just quickly. So how would you define the concept of cost effectiveness within serverless? Like, what does that mean to you when you hear the word cost effective?

Participant: What that means is... hm... pay for what you use. And it also means... quick iteration times when developing.

Edvin: Yep, that's a solid answer. I'll move on to the next question. So can you provide an example of a situation where you identified a cost inefficiency in testing and how did you address that?

Participant: Cost inefficiency in testing... specifically with regards to serverless than, I take it?

Edvin: Yeah.

Participant: Or it okay– No... I don't think s– ...in a sense one cost inefficiency is that when the integration tests you for– For running tests against rest APIs, when the test gets large it takes a long time to run it and that become, that makes the iteration times for me as a developer long. That is cost inefficient with regards to my salary.

Edvin: Yeah. *Short laughter.*

Participant: And in that case what– and together to get around that. That's the case of. What we've done then is to introduce more unit tests and reduce the number of API tests. So shifting the type of tests because we were just creating too many like the value per individual API test was getting pretty small.

Edvin: I just wanted to ask, as a pseudo follow up I guess: when you think of the issue of– Because when you test something that involves the serverless component, each test will sort of cost money like literal money right? Because–

Participant: We haven't had that– we– all the serverless tech that we created has been internal facing, developer facing and because of that, costs never– like operating costs and call costs, API call costs, never become a significant factor.

Edvin: Okay.

Participant: It's just not enough activity. But we're talking like, well, it's because– it's because we make a couple of 1000 calls a week to the cloud function. We're not doing millions or billions calls a week, okay.

Edvin: So it's just not that much budget being drained.

Participant: Exactly.

Edvin: Yeah, okay. All right. What strategies will you use to manage and reduce costs for serverless testing?

Participant: For serverless testing specifically.

Edvin: Yeah.

Participant: Yeah... I don't have any good answers there.

Edvin: Mm hm.

Participant: Do you need something?

Edvin: Should we nudge him in any way, Greg?

Gregory: Yeah, we do need something. Ok. Like, like, yeah, like any sort of like metric that you would use or any sort of I guess like any sort of like external factor that makes you believe that there is another way of doing something like what you mentioned before with switching from units to from integration to units– unit testing. Yeah, i'll just say like external factors, anything?

Participant: Yeah, okay. So, things that make us change how we test. Like if developer iteration times turn into... like it takes more than a minute to run a test suit, then like, then we need to change our approach. That's the primary thing that we see at the moment when it comes to testing.

Gregory: Okay. All right. All right.

Edvin: Okay. So we just move on then?

Gregory: Yeah.

Edvin: Because I was thinking– I was thinking we also have– we could bring up the concepts that we have in our survey. I was thinking–

Gregory: Yeah, sure.

Edvin: Because we have mentioned some strategies in our server we have that it's not relevant to you but, we mentioned things like centralized logging, organizational maturity, product maturity, testing in parallel, so like multiple tests running at the same time and also configuration of the CI/CD pipelines for automation–automated testing. So those are some strategies that we've heard before and we've included in that. Does that– Get you thinking in any way? Any opinions on what you just heard?

Participant: Can you repeat that? *Laughs*

Edvin: *Laughs* Yeah, I'm sorry, it was like 5 things! Yeah. Centralized logging system, organizational maturity, product maturity, testing in parallel, and CI/CD pipelines for automated testing.

Participant: Okay product maturity first. Serverless tech is very good for getting something rolling. It's very good for if you need a solution for a limited amount of time. Sometimes someone wants to have a marketing website up for a month and they need a bunch of logic that is connected to that marketing website. There's a login flow and you're supposed to be able to register and then it's going to send a bunch of emails and then once that entire marketing event is over, that no longer has any value. It's fantastic to use serverless tech for something like that. If you're going to build a web application, you're going to build the mobile app and the purpose of you— for you to build, of building this mobile app is to convince someone to give you a shit ton of money so that you can build the mobile app that you actually want to build. Then serverless tech is a great thing to start with, even despite, like the thing that you actually want to build is totally unsuited for that technology choice because of reasons. Then maybe you're just going to, maybe you're going to be able to bag that bag of money, easier by using the serverless tech and once you have that bag of money then you can— then you can spend the extra time of doing it all from scratch by doing it properly at that point.

Edvin: So when you say the serverless is great for those, it's like quick to develop and efficient and to then maintain and stuff, okay.

Participant: Yes, quick initial time to market, it's good for that. It's good for glue. Yeah?

Gregory: Would you say that monolithic applications are quicker or would you say that serverless applications are quicker? So it depends on the use case.

Participant: Sorry. Would you say that, what? Repeat it please.

Gregory: Because would you say that monolithic applications are also a good way, like— like if you have the choice, would you choose like would you still choose serverless given that there are monolithic applications?

Participant: I would make the choice depending on how much logic there is inside of the application. Because serverless makes all the things like on the application— how do I put it? On the surface of the application it makes that easier.

Gregory: Okay.

Participant: So on the other hand— on the other hand if— once you start to need the series like CPU compute power for example. Then you'll find that using lots of compute power inside of serverless functions. Typically you pay more for that, than if you're going let's rent the machine and have my application somehow running on that machine.

Edvin: Okay, but I guess we can move on from the strategy question. And then we have this other one which is what are the key test metrics you monitor in the system, in the serverless system.

Participant: Test metrics... I monitor like when it comes to production then it's like error rates and when it comes to test suits then... I look at how long does it take to run the test, do all tests pass: yes or no. And also what's the response time for each individual test?

Edvin: Is there any metric—

Gregory: Uh—

Edvin: Yeah, go.

Gregory: No no, no. Yeah, after you finish that question.

Edvin: Like is there any— if you could like have— what's what's like the most vital metric if you had to pick one?

Participant: The most vital metric here, that's like do all the tests pass, yes or no? Because to a large extent testing to me is about me validating that I wrote code that is good and proper. And again, we're not doing things at the scale where like response times, they don't tend to fluctuate for us. Like memory usage doesn't spike and so on.

Edvin: Cuz some other participants will have answered like response time is very important but that's because they also it costed a lot more for them to use serverless. As you mentioned it was kinda— it wasn't a big budgetary—

Participant: Yeah they're like they're writing green software. We're gluing things together with it. Okay.

Google Meet notification sound, warning about the limited time available.

Edvin: Oh shit, we have only 10 minutes in the call.

Gregory: Okay. I'll ask my question real quick so if you— Because— What are the differences and similarities within testing serverless applications and microservices? We had a question from our examiner about how, uh... yeah, like it's achieving cost effectiveness within serverless applications. A lot of the same problem— Some of the same problems are also inherent within microservices. So we're wondering what you were thinking, what you would say about this?

Participant: When you're testing microservices then... aah...? I know that almost feels like a trick question. I'm trying to think of some kind of relevant: okay serverless here, microservices here. There should be some axis you can slice along, but—

Gregory: But yeah, because at the end of the day— Yeah, sorry— Yeah, because at the end of the day, they both do the same thing. They decompose bigger tasks into smaller tasks, but within serverless it's on the more granular level where it's functioned instead of services. So yeah, and then there's a lot of latency as well between both microservices because they communicate through a certain remote procedure call. But then within serverless it gets through CP? requests.

Participant: But what you mentioned there is actually a good point. When people construct microservices, they are like the logic is in larger chunks and there's often code— code and— logic and databases are often collocated.

Gregory: Yup.

Participant: Whereas within serverless typically we have a function is over here and the database is over there. So uhm... there are more hops... there are more hops when you like, build serverless stuff, which means there are more places where latency can creep up. So yeah, so like my take on it is that doing microservices instead like that enables you to, it gives you more flexibility, more freedom, you can collocate things to a larger extent. And you can work around architecture performance problems.

Gregory: I'll make a quick Google Meet, because we're running out of time.

Participant: Well, unfortunately, I don't have more time, so.

Gregory: Yeah, yeah, perfect, perfect.

Edvin: We only have two questions left...?

Gregory: Ok, then one quick, one last quick question. Sorry—

Edvin: Better be quick. *Laughs.*

Gregory: But can you quickly explain the like? How does it differ with making test cases when it comes to microservices versus serverless?

Participant: I don't think there is a particular difference in it.

Gregory: Okay.

Edvin: Yeah, let's move on. So we have this one. How do you ensure the testing environment is optimized for cost efficiency while still being representative of the production environment? A bit vague, but—

Participant: Yeah. I just say that there is nothing unique to serverless tech in that respect. So it's yeah the same exact problem if you're doing a monolith or like doing a bunch of microservices or using something like that.

Edvin: Uhm, okay, I don't know if that answered the question– what– because... We asked about if you optimize, like, uh... how do you ensure that the test environment is optimized for cost efficiency while also representing the final order?

Participant: “Jadu”, It should be like this. It's like “how long is a piece of string”-type question. So uhm, because it's entirely dependent on what you're doing, but you're gonna start out making sure that it's like functionally complete. That's step 1, step 2 is... make sure that you can throw enough traffic through it,

Edvin: Okay.

Participant: And like once you get those two covered, then you're probably in a good position.

Edvin: Okay, that's fine. That's a good answer actually. So should we just go to the last question, which is a very short question. So simply, do you know of any emerging trends or technologies that revolves around serverless testing or is there anything you wish for?

Participant: I wish for this for K-native to become an even more mature tool. So that i can run my serverless shit on the Kubernetes cluster. *Laughs.*

Edvin: *Laughs.* Okay. That's a fair wish. Yeah, I guess that's all the questions then. You happy Gregory?

Gregory: Yeah, I'm happy. I'm happy! Is it okay if we ask you some follow up questions? Like if we need to? Sweet.

Edvin: I should not end the recording yet?

Gregory: I mean f– I'm good.

Edvin: Ok, yes. Then I'm just gonna end the recording, if it's not relevant to the–

Gregory: Go for it!

Edvin: Ok, I'm ending it.

Gregory: Go!

END OF RECORDING.